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Vector boson scattering measurements in ATLAS

Shu Li^{a,b,c}, *On behalf of the ATLAS collaboration*

^aTsung-Dao Lee Institute, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 520 Shengrong Road, Shanghai 201210, China

^bInstitute of Nuclear and Particle Physics, School of Physics and Astronomy, Key Laboratory for Particle Astrophysics and Cosmology (MOE), Shanghai Key Laboratory for Particle Physics and Cosmology (SKLPPC), Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 800 Dongchuan Road, Shanghai 200240, China

^cCenter for High Energy Physics, Peking University, 5 Yiheyuan Road, Beijing 100871, China

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Abstract

In this talk, we present the latest progresses in measuring the Vector Boson Scattering processes in Standard Model with ATLAS experiment at the Large Hadron Collider. The most recent results of the $ZZ \rightarrow 4\ell$, $Z(\rightarrow \ell^+\ell^-)\gamma$, like-sign $W^\pm W^\pm$ and opposite-sign $W^\pm W^\mp$ channels with Vector Boson Scattering topologies are shown.

Vector Boson Scatterings (VBS), being the rare processes in Standard Model (SM) Electroweak interactions, are the keys to understand the nature of SM Electroweak Symmetry Breaking (EWSB) and Higgs properties in unitarization of the weak boson scattering processes. To observe and measure precisely the VBS processes and properties in SM will help to not only greatly consolidating in general the SM theory in the Electroweak sector, but also in particular the Higgs mechanism in SM VBS processes which have the longitudinally polarized weak bosons directly connected to the Higgs. Therefore, the VBS physics has been one of the long term flagship topics in LHC Electroweak physics with many interesting milestone results obtained by both ATLAS and CMS collaborations in the LHC experiment.

In this talk, we present the latest progresses in VBS physics at ATLAS on behalf of the collaboration: the VBS measurements in $ZZ \rightarrow 4\ell$, $Z(\rightarrow \ell^+\ell^-)\gamma$, like-sign $W^\pm W^\pm$ and opposite-sign $W^\pm W^\mp$ channels in association with two forward jets, while the opposite-sign $W^\pm W^\mp$ VBS processes are measured for the first time with more than $5\text{-}\sigma$ significance leading to the first observation of such process at ATLAS.

VBS processes are among those subprocesses with pure electroweak coupling vertices at tree level in SM, with typical signatures of two incoming vector bosons and two outgoing vector bosons while two quark partons are propagated to the final states presented by two forward jets originating from electroweak interactions instead of hadronic interactions. When measuring the VBS processes, the other non-VBS processes generated by electroweak interactions are measured along. One may not separate the VBS from the non-VBS electroweak processes because of gauge invariance preservation. But we can introduce VBS sensitive experimental observables to be used for the measured phasespace construction so the VBS contributions in such phasespaces can be enhanced, e.g. by requiring two forward jets in the final states (Figure 1).

Figure 1: VBS experimental topologies.

The VBS ZZ process was for the first time measured with more than $5\text{-}\sigma$ significance at the LHC by the ATLAS experiment, by combining the charged four lepton decay channels and two charged lepton plus two neutrino channels [1]. In the latest results of this channel from ATLAS [2], the full Run-2 dataset of 140 fb^{-1} is used for further differential measurement in the high purity charged four lepton final states. The unfolded differential cross sections are in agreement with state-of-art predictions for both QCD and Electroweak $ZZjj$ enriched regions 2. Differential cross sections are used to search for anomalous couplings using dimension-6 and dimension-8 EFT operators. A cut-off that prevents unitarity violation (UV) at large energy scales is considered with calculated UV bounds [3].

Figure 2: Measured inclusive $4\ell jj$ production differential cross sections as a function of dijet invariant mass in the VBS enhanced (left) and suppressed (right) regions [2].

The VBS processes are also studied in the $Z(\rightarrow \ell\ell)\gamma$ final states differentially using the full dataset of ATLAS Run-2 [5], following up the first observation result [4]. Two differentially measured phasespaces are probed with VBS enriched selection and extended phasespace covering also low dijet mass region³. Such measurements cover both the electroweak only components and QCD+Electroweak components inclusively, the latter of which include also the interference effects of QCD and electroweak components.

Figure 3: Measured $Z\gamma jj$ differential cross sections as a function of dijet invariant mass in the signal region (left) and extended signal region (right) [5].

The like-sign $W^\pm W^\mp$ channel is one of the golden channels to probe the VBS process because the suppression of QCD induced backgrounds already at tree level. Following up the first observation of such process in ATLAS [6], a full Run-2 dataset analysis has been performed with not only more precise measurements of integrated electroweak and total fiducial cross sections but also the first differential measurement of this channel is achieved [7]. Limits on dimension-8 EFT operators to probe

aQGC limits are set with and without UV preservation treatment (cut-off scale of 1.5TeV and compare with UV bound) while the limit evolution as a function of the cut-off scales is also carefully scanned 4. Besides, the limits on the production of fermiophobic doubly charged $H^{\pm\pm}$ decaying to a pair of W bosons, within the GeorgiMachacek (GM) model are also obtained 4.

Figure 4: aQGC (left) and GM fermiophobic doubly charged $H^{\pm\pm}$ (right) limits [7].

The opposite-sign $W^{\pm}W^{\mp}$ channel VBS process is for the first time observed at ATLAS with more than $5\text{-}\sigma$ significance [8], marking a great milestone in ATLAS VBS Physics. Two neural networks are trained to distinguish signal from largest backgrounds: top and QCD induced $WWjj$ production. The observed and expected significances are 7.1σ and 6.2σ respectively while combining the 2/3 jet bins in the measured phase space 5.

Figure 5: Distributions of the NN output in the signal regions for 2-jet (left) and 3-jet (right), respectively [8].

In conclusion, further precise measurements of total and electroweak cross sections are for the first time performed in many VBS channels in ATLAS after observations, providing more solid tests of SM predic-

tions and unique probe to BSM signatures related to gauge boson self-interactions and beyond. Both unitarized and non-unitarized limits are set on EFT high dimension operators to probe aQGCs in VBS processes. More physics interest are to be explored in the future. such as longitudinal polarization, combined limits on aQGCs, etc.

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